

AML of Complete Bipartite Graph and Constraint on AML for Cyclic Graphs

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Abstract: In this paper the AML for all Bipartite Graphs and the limit of the Ameliorated Mean Labeling on cyclic graphs are studied.

Keywords: AML, Bipartite graph and cyclic graph.

I. INTRODUCTION

A Labeling of a graph is the assignment of distinct integers to the vertices or edges or both, subject to certain conditions. The origin of labeling traces to β - evaluation introduced by Rosa. It was introduced in mid 1960s. Over 200 graph labelings have been studied since. Ameliorated Mean Labeling was introduced by Silviya Francis[3] and few basic results have been studied.

II. AMELIORATED MEAN GRAPH

A graph with p vertices and q edges is said to be an Ameliorated mean graph if there exists a function g from the vertex set of G to $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, q\}$ such that the induced map g^* from the edge set of G to $\{1, 2, \dots, q\}$ defined by

$$g^*(e = uv) = \begin{cases} \frac{g(u) + g(v) + 1}{2} & \text{if one of } g(u) \text{ and } g(v) \text{ is odd and the other is even;} \\ \frac{|g(u) - g(v)|}{2} & \text{if } g(u) \text{ and } g(v) \text{ both are either odd or even;} \end{cases}$$

then all the resulting edges get distinct labels from the set $\{1, 2, \dots, q\}$. Such that the function g is injection and g^* is bijection [3].

2.1. Theorem: All complete bipartite graphs $K_{v,\omega}$ are Ameliorated Mean Graphs.

Proof: A complete bipartite graph $K_{v,\omega}$ has $v + \omega$ vertices and $v\omega$ edges.

To prove that a complete bipartite graph $K_{v,\omega}$ is an ameliorated mean graph, we have to define a function from the vertex set(V) and edge set(E) of the complete bipartite graph, $g : V \rightarrow 0, 1, \dots, v\omega$ and $g^* : E \rightarrow 1, \dots, v\omega$ respectively, such that g is injection and g^* is bijection. To prove that, the Ameliorated Mean Labeling of all $K_{v,\omega}$ are disintegrated under four cases.

Case i: v is odd and ω is odd.

Case ii: v is odd and ω is even.

Case iii: v is even and ω is odd.

Case iv: v is even and ω is even.

In all the four cases v, ω are considered to be $v \leq \omega$.

How any $K_{v,\omega}$ falls exactly in one type? For explanation let us consider $K_{v,\omega}, 1 \leq v, \omega \leq 5$ all graphs are given by,

$K_{1,1}$	$K_{1,2}$	$K_{1,3}$	$K_{1,4}$	$K_{1,5}$
$K_{2,1}$	$K_{2,2}$	$K_{2,3}$	$K_{2,4}$	$K_{2,5}$
$K_{3,1}$	$K_{3,2}$	$K_{3,3}$	$K_{3,4}$	$K_{3,5}$
$K_{4,1}$	$K_{4,2}$	$K_{4,3}$	$K_{4,4}$	$K_{4,5}$
$K_{5,1}$	$K_{5,2}$	$K_{5,3}$	$K_{5,4}$	$K_{5,5}$

The above matrix is symmetric with respect to Ameliorated mean labeling, since the labeling of $K_{v,\omega}$ is same as the labeling of $K_{\omega,v}$. (Also, the graphs below the diagonals are $v > \omega$.) Hence its enough to prove that each graphs above the diagonals lie exactly in only one of the cases.

$K_{1,1}$	$K_{1,2}$	$K_{1,3}$	$K_{1,4}$	$K_{1,5}$
	$K_{2,2}$	$K_{2,3}$	$K_{2,4}$	$K_{2,5}$
		$K_{3,3}$	$K_{3,4}$	$K_{3,5}$
			$K_{4,4}$	$K_{4,5}$
				$K_{5,5}$

In the above matrix, the graphs $K_{1,1}, K_{1,3}, K_{1,5}, K_{3,3}, K_{3,5}, K_{5,5}$ lies in the first case, $K_{1,2}, K_{1,4}, K_{3,4}$ lies in the second case, $K_{2,3}, K_{2,5}, K_{4,5}$ lies in the third case and $K_{2,2}, K_{2,4}, K_{4,4}$ lies in the fourth case. Hence each graphs of $K_{v,\omega}, 1 \leq v, \omega \leq 5$ lies exactly in one of the four cases. Therefore, by induction it is clear that all the complete bipartite graphs $K_{v,\omega}$ lies exactly in one case when $v \leq \omega$.

Now, to prove the theorem the vertex labeling and edge labeling of four cases are given below.

Case i: v is odd and ω is odd.

The vertex labeling of $K_{v,\omega}$, when v is odd and ω is odd, is given as follows.

FIGURE 1. Eg. of Case: i AML of $K_{3,5}$

$$g(u_i) = q - 2i + 1, 1 \leq i \leq v$$

$$g(v_j) = v(2j - 1) - 1, 1 \leq j \leq \lfloor \frac{\omega}{2} \rfloor$$

$$g(v_k) = q - 2v \left(k - \lfloor \frac{\omega}{2} \rfloor \right), \lfloor \frac{\omega}{2} \rfloor \leq k \leq \omega.$$

The edge labeling for this case is given as follows.

In this case v and ω are odd, hence $q = v\omega$ is odd. Then, vertex labeling $g(u_i)$ is even; $g(v_j), 1 \leq j \leq \lfloor \frac{\omega}{2} \rfloor$ is even and $g(v_k), \lfloor \frac{\omega}{2} \rfloor \leq k \leq \omega$ is odd. So, for the edge labels

$$g * (u_i v_j) = \frac{|q - m(2j - 1) - 2i + 2|}{2} \text{ and for the edge labels } g * (u_i v_k) = q - m \left(k - \lfloor \frac{\omega}{2} \rfloor \right) - i + 1.$$

Hence the edge labeling are $1, 2, \dots, q$. Hence, $K_{v,\omega}$, when v is odd and ω is odd is an AMG.

Case ii: v is odd and ω is even.

The vertex labeling of $K_{v,\omega}$, when v is odd and ω is even, is given as follows.

FIGURE 2. Eg. of Case: ii AML of $K_{3,6}$

$$g(u_i) = q - 2i + 1, 1 \leq i \leq v$$

$$g(v_j) = v(2j - 1) - 3, 1 \leq j \leq \frac{\omega}{2} + 1$$

$$g(v_k) = 2v(k - 1) - q - 1, \frac{\omega}{2} + 2 \leq k \leq \omega.$$

The edge labeling for this case is given as follows.

In this case v is odd and ω is even, hence $q = v\omega$ is even. Then, vertex labeling $g(u_i)$ is odd; $g(v_j), 1 \leq j \leq \frac{\omega}{2} + 1$ is even and $g(v_k), \frac{\omega}{2} + 2 \leq k \leq \omega$ is odd. So, for the edge labels $g * (u_i v_j) = \frac{q - 2i + m(2j - 1) - 1}{2}$ and for the edge labels $g * (u_i v_k) = q - m(k - 1) - i + 1$. Hence the edge labeling are $1, 2, \dots, q$. Hence, $K_{v,\omega}$, when v is odd and ω is even is an AMG.

Case iii: v is even and ω is odd.

The vertex labeling of $K_{v,\omega}$, when v is even and ω is odd, is given as follows.

$$g(v_i) = 2i, 1 \leq i \leq \omega$$

$$g(u_j) = q - 1 - 2\omega(j - 1), 1 \leq j \leq \frac{v}{2}$$

$$g(u_k) = 2\omega \left(k - \frac{v}{2} - 1\right), \frac{v}{2} + 1 \leq k \leq v.$$

The edge labeling for this case is given as follows, In this case v is even and ω is odd, hence $q = v\omega$ is even. Then, vertex labeling $g(v_i), 1 \leq i \leq \omega$ is even; $g(u_j), 1 \leq j \leq \frac{v}{2}$ is odd and $g(v_k), \frac{v}{2} + 1 \leq k \leq v$ is even. So, for the edge labels $g * (v_i u_j) = q - i - n(j - 1) + 1$ and for the edge labels $g * (v_i u_k) = q - n(j - 1) - i + 1$.

Hence the edge labeling are $1, 2, \dots, q$. Hence, $K_{v,\omega}$, when v is even and ω is odd is an AMG.

Case iv: v is even and ω is even.

The vertex labeling of $K_{v,\omega}$, when v is even and ω is even, is given as follows.

FIGURE 3. Eg. of Case: iii AML of $K_{4,5}$

$$g(u_i) = q - (2i - 2), 1 \leq i \leq v$$

$$g(v_i) = q - 1 - 2v(i - 1), 1 \leq i \leq \frac{\omega}{2}$$

$$g(v_j) = 2v \left(j - \frac{\omega}{2} - 1\right), \frac{\omega}{2} + 1 \leq j \leq \omega.$$

The edge labeling for this case is given as follows. In this case v is even and ω is even, hence $q = v\omega$ is even. Then, vertex labeling $g(u_i), 1 \leq i \leq v$ is even; $g(v_j), 1 \leq i \leq \frac{\omega}{2}$ is odd and $g(v_k), \frac{\omega}{2} + 1 \leq j \leq \omega$ is even. So, for the edge labels $g * (u_i v_j) = q - i - m(j - 1) + 1$ and for the edge labels $g * (u_i v_k) = q - m(k - 1) - i + 1$. Hence the edge labeling are $1, 2, \dots, q$. Hence, $K_{v,\omega}$, when v is even and ω is even is an AMG.

2.2 Lemma: All bipartite graphs $K_{v,\omega}$ are AMG.

This lemma can be proved by replacing v and ω in the previous theorem by the sum of degrees of vertices in both the partite sets respectively.

2.3 Theorem A Cycle graph C_n is an AML if and only if $n \leq 4$.

Proof: Let us first prove that C_n is an AML if $n \leq 4$. The AML of C_3, C_4 are given in figure 5. Secondly, it has to be proved that C_n is not an AML if $n \geq 5$. To prove this, let us first prove that C_5 is not an AML. Let us consider the contradiction. Suppose, C_5 is an AML.

FIGURE 4. Eg. of Case: iv AML of $K_{2,6}$

FIGURE 5. AML of C_3 and C_4

FIGURE 6. C_5

C_5 have 5 vertex and 5 edges. Therefore, the vertices should be labelled from

$\{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ distinctively i.e., the function on the vertex set, $g : V(G) \Rightarrow \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ should be injection. And the function on the edge set, $g : E(G) \Rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ should be bijection.

The vertices and edges of C_5 are denoted as $\{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5\}$ and $\{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4, e_5\}$ respectively (Fig.6).

There are more than one possible pair of vertex labels to get the edge 1,2,3,4 but there is only one vertex label pair to induce the edge label 5, they are 4 and 5. Hence, let us start the vertex labeling by labeling $v_1 = 5$ and $v_2 = 4$, thence $e_1 = 5$. Next, to induce the edge labeling 4, the possible vertex label pairs are 4 – 3 (3 – 4) and 5 – 2 (2 – 5).

Case: i Considering the first pair 4 – 3 to induce the edge label 4, then

$v_3 = 3 \Rightarrow e_2 = 4$. To get the edge label 3, the possible vertex labeling pairs are 0 – 5, 1 – 4, 2 – 3 and vice versa. With $v_1 = 5, v_2 = 4,$ and $v_3 = 3$, the second option 1 – 4 is deleted because there is no unlabeled vertex available neighbour to the vertex labeled 4.

FIGURE 7. Case: i. a & b

Case: i. a Now, considering the first option 0 – 5 to get the edge label 3, since, $v_1 = 5$ the unlabeled neighbour v_5 can be labeled 0, therefore $e_5 = 3$. The remaining unlabeled vertex v_4 should be labeled with any one of the numbers $\{1, 2\}$ since all the other labels $\{0, 3, 4, 5\}$ are already labeled. If $v_4 = 1$, with $v_3 = 3$ and $v_5 = 0, e_4 = 1$ and $e_3 = 1$ which is a contradiction to the definition of AML, the edge function should be bijection. Hence, C_5 is not an AML when $v_4 = 1$. If $v_4 = 2$ then $e_4 = 1, e_3 = 3$, contradicting the definition of AML, since $e_5 = 3$. Hence, C_5 is not an AML when $v_4 = 2$.

Case: i. b Consider the third option 2 – 3, on inducing the edge label 3. The unlabelled vertex adjacent to the vertex labelled 3 ($v_3 = 3$) is v_4 , therefore, let $v_4 = 2 \Rightarrow e_3 = 3. v_5$ should be labeled as such e_4 and e_5 are distinctly $\{1, 2\}. v_5 \in \{0, 1\}$. With $v_4 = 2$ and $v_1 = 5$; if $v_5 = 0$ then $e_4 = 1$ and $e_5 = 3$. Hence, the contradiction since, $e_5 = 3$; If $v_5 = 1$ then $e_4 = 2$ and $e_5 = 2$ hence the contradiction. Therefore, C_5 is not an AML in these cases too.

Case: ii Considering the second pair 5 – 2 to induce the edge label 4, then $v_5 = 2 \Rightarrow e_5 = 4$. To get the edge label 3, the possible vertex labeling pairs are 0 – 5, 1 – 4, 2 – 3 and vice versa. With $v_1 = 5, v_2 = 4, v_5 = 2$, the first option 0 – 5 is deleted because there is no unlabeled vertex available neighbour to the vertex labeled 5.

Case: ii. a Now, considering the second option 1 – 4, since, $v_2 = 4$ the unlabeled neighbour v_3 can be labeled 1, therefore $e_2 = 3$. The remaining unlabeled vertex v_4 should be labeled with any one of the elements $\{0, 3\}$ since all the other labels $\{0, 3, 4, 5\}$ are already labeled. If $v_4 = 0$, with $v_3 = 1$ and $v_5 = 2$, $e_3 = 1$ and $e_4 = 1$ which is a contradiction to the definition of AML (the edge function should be bijection). Hence, C_5 is not an AML in this case. If $v_4 = 3$ then $e_3 = 1$, $e_4 = 3$, contradiction since we already have $e_2 = 3$. Hence, C_5 is not an AML in this case too.

Case: ii. b Consider the third option 2 – 3, let $v_4 = 3 \Rightarrow e_4 = 3$. Then v_3 should be labeled as such e_2 and e_3 are $\{1, 2\}$. Then v_3 shall be labelled with one in $\{0, 1\}$. With $v_4 = 3$ and $v_2 = 4$; if $v_3 = 0$ then $e_2 = 2$ and $e_3 = 2$. Hence, the contradiction. If $v_3 = 1$ then $e_2 = 3$ and $e_3 = 1$ hence the contradiction, since $e_4 = 3$. Therefore, C_5 is not an AMG in these cases too. Hence, it is proved that C_5 is not an AMG. With a similar proof it can be proved that C_6 is not an AMG. With a similar argument it can be proved that C_n is not an AML when $n \geq 5$.

FIGURE 8. Case: ii. a & b

III. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have exclusively classified complete bipartite graphs into four categories and provided the ameliorated mean labeling for each type. Additionally, we have defined the constraints for cyclic graphs in the context of AML.

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